

SPACE TIME STRUCTURE OF NEUTRAL CURRENT

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After the discussion¹ at the last neutrino conference, the possibility that neutral current interaction of ν 's may not be pure V, A has been entertained seriously. Here I present some work of Rajasekaran and myself² on the general phenomenological analysis of the inclusive process

$$\nu(\bar{\nu}) + N \rightarrow \nu(\bar{\nu}) + \text{anything}$$

taking all the covariants V, A, S, P, T into account. Note that S, P, T would imply a) helicity flip of neutrino, b) possibility of non-zero neutrino mass, c) a connection between P violation and T violation and d) difficulty in constructing unified gauge models.

Assuming time reversal invariance and noting that incident ν 's are polarized, the most general effective (non-derivative) neutral ν -hadron interaction becomes

$$\frac{G}{\sqrt{2}} \{ \bar{\nu} \gamma_{\alpha} \nu (V^{\alpha} + A^{\alpha}) + \bar{\nu} \nu S + i \bar{\nu} \gamma_5 \nu P + \bar{\nu} \sigma_{\alpha\beta} \nu T^{\alpha\beta} \} \quad (1)$$

V, A and S, P, T do not interfere in the cross sections. There are 9 additional structure functions from S, P, T interactions. In terms of these the double differential cross section is

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{d^2\sigma(v^{\pm}N)}{dx dy} = & \frac{G^2 m_N E}{8\pi} [xy^2\{W_7 + W_8\} + 4\{\frac{E^2}{2m_N} x(2-y)^2 y^2 W_{12} \\ & + 4\frac{EY}{m_N}(1-y)W_{13} - 2\frac{E}{m_N} x^2 y^3 W_{14} + 2\frac{E}{m_N} xy^3 W_{15}\} \\ & \pm 4\frac{E}{m_N} xy^2(2-y)\{W_9 + W_{10}\}] \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

The v , A cross section can be just added on to this. Here $E = E_v$ in lab, x and y are the usual scaling variables

$x = \frac{|q^2|}{2m_N v}$, $y = v/E$, $v^+ = v$, $v^- = \bar{v}$; and the structure functions $W_i = W_i(q^2, v)$. W_7 and W_8 are SS and PP; W_9, W_{10} are ST and PT; and W_{11} to W_{15} are TT. This formula is too general to be useful at present.

Assuming Bjorken scaling, i.e., as $v \rightarrow \infty$, $|q^2| \rightarrow \infty$ and x finite, W_i 's are assumed to scale as:

$$\begin{aligned} (W_7, W_8, W_{11}) & \rightarrow (F_7, F_8, F_{11}) \\ \frac{v}{m_N}(W_9, W_{10}, W_{13}, W_{14}, W_{15}) & \rightarrow (F_9, F_{10}, F_{13}, F_{14}, F_{15}) \\ \frac{v^2}{m_N} W_{12} & \rightarrow F_{12} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where $F_i = F_i(x)$, the total cross section becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma(v^{\pm}N) = & \frac{G^2 m_N E}{24\pi} \int_0^1 dx [x\{F_7 + F_8\} \\ & + 4\{7x F_{12} + 6F_{13} - 2x^2 F_{14} + 2x F_{15}\} \pm 8x\{F_9 + F_{10}\}] \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

By using positivity constraints on F_i , it is possible to

$$\text{bound } R = \frac{\sigma(vN)}{\sigma(\bar{v}N)} \text{ by}^2$$

$$0.1389 \leq R \leq 7.195 \quad (5)$$

to be compared to the bounds 3 and 1/3 in the V, A case.

Hence if R lies outside (1/3, 3) some S, P, T must be present.

In a specific quark-parton model all of F_i 's can be explicitly calculated in terms of the couplings of v 's to the quarks. Assuming antiquark and strange-quark contribution to be small we obtain for scattering off $I = 0$ target

$$\frac{d^2\sigma(v^\pm N)}{dx dy} = \frac{G^2 m_N E}{16\pi} [\phi_\pm^u(y) + \phi_\pm^d(y)] \times Q(x) \quad (6)$$

where

$$Q(x) = \frac{U(x) + D(x)}{2}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \phi_\pm^u(y) = & [2(h_V^u \pm h_A^u)^2 + 2(h_V^u \mp h_A^u)^2 (1-y)^2 \\ & + 8 h_T^{u^2} (2-y)^2 + (h_S^u + h_P^u)^2 y^2 \mp 4 h_T^u (h_S^u - h_P^u) y(2-y)] \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

$\phi_\pm^d(y)$ is defined similarly and $U(x)$ ($D(x)$) is the probability of finding the u-quark (d-quark) in the proton with fractional momentum x . It is easy to see from the above that S, P, T can fake any y distribution that V, A can produce.^{3,4} What is not so obvious is that the reverse is not true, i.e., V, A cannot reproduce every combination of y distribution in v and \bar{v} reactions.² This is useful as follows: Parametrize y distributions of v and \bar{v} as

$$\frac{d\sigma(\nu N)}{dy} = A + By + Cy^2 \quad (8a)$$

$$\frac{d\sigma(\bar{\nu} N)}{dy} = A + \bar{B}y + \bar{C}y^2 \quad (8b)$$

Then

$$C + \bar{C} - A = 2\alpha(h_S^2 + h_P^2 - 8h_T^2) \quad (9)$$

where

$$\alpha = \int_0^1 \frac{G^2 m_N E}{16\pi} \times Q(x) dx$$

Hence if experimentally $C + \bar{C} - A \neq 0$, some S, P, T must be present.²

We have also looked at possible couplings of ν 's to integer spin partons^{2,5} inside the nucleon (e.g., color gluons). In general this leads to σ_T scaling as E_L^2 and y^3 terms in the y distributions. Bounds on R also change:

$$0.0697 < R < 14.33 \quad J = 1, \quad S, P, T$$

$$1/6 < R < 6 \quad J = 1, \quad V, A$$

As mentioned earlier, P violation implies T violation. Another possibility is to have "non-diagonal" couplings.⁶ Both of these can be tested in exclusive reactions such as $\nu N \rightarrow \nu N\pi$, $\nu N \rightarrow \nu AK$, etc.^{6,7}

Finally, I would like to mention a possible check of S versus V in ν interaction. This is in ν excitation of the 6.1 MeV 0^+ level of 0^{16} . The Scalar is expected to give cross sections higher (by a factor of 20 - 100) than the

vector and may be almost in the observable range (e.g., $\sigma \approx 10^{-42} \text{ cm}^2$ at $E_\nu = 50 \text{ MeV}$). The decay signature being pure e^+e^- offers a further advantage.⁸

References

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